

White Paper

I-SEAMORE™

**Business Modelling for an
advanced platform
managing
maritime surveillance operations**

06/09/2025

Business Modelling for an advanced platform managing maritime surveillance operation

Project Title: Integrated surveillance ecosystem for European Authorities responsible for Maritime Operations leveraged by reliable and enhanced aerial support

Project Acronym: I-SEAMORE

Grant Agreement number: HE 101073911

Authors: Dr. h.c. Wolfgang KNIEJSKI (INI-Novation GmbH)
Ms. Angela IVANOVA (INI-Novation GmbH)

Version 1.0

AUTHORS

Wolfgang Kniejski started his business career in 1991 as the Financial Manager of Fraunhofer Institute for Computer Graphics, in Darmstadt, Germany. In 1999 he took the position as Business Manager of INI-GraphicsNet Foundation, since 2004 he was appointed as its Treasurer and Business Director. In this capacity he developed and successfully implemented methodologies and processes to support the technology commercialisation for universities and research institutions via licensing and spin-off activities. Dr. Kniejski spun his technology commercialisation knowledge off into his own company and created INI-Novation GmbH as an innovation and IP management and consulting entity.

Angela Ivanova has more than 25 years of experience as a business executive and 20 years of experience in management of market research projects and PR campaigns in her own private company. Ms. Ivanova gained experiences as consultant and coach in strategic communications, marketing, creativity, education and innovation for SMEs and start-ups. In September 2014 Angela Ivanova started working at Business Development Director in INI-Novation GmbH Germany. Ms. Angela Ivanova is an internationally recognised expert for the development of market analysis and concepts for the establishment of innovative infrastructures. In the course of many successful projects, she has established a very vital and effective partnership network in different places all over Europe.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank all project partners and interviewees who gave us important suggestions and practical information during the preparation of this white paper.

Special thanks are extended to:

- **Ricard Munné (ATOS)** for the very efficient cooperation and guidance as I-SEAMORE's project coordinator.
- **All technical project partners from I-SEAMORE and the end users** for guiding us through the technical architecture and its values.
- **F6S and ISIG** for the valuable discussion, especially on barriers for commercial exploitation.

Thank you for the very constructive and efficient cooperation!

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Authors.....	2
Table of contents.....	3
1 Introduction.....	4
1.1 Scope.....	4
1.2 Synopsis and methods of our approach.....	4
2 Stakeholder focus.....	6
3 I-SEAMORE system architecture and use cases.....	7
3.1 System description.....	7
3.2 Use cases.....	9
3.2.1 Detecting unauthorized border crossing:.....	9
3.2.2 Preventing smuggling of drugs.....	10
3.2.3 Other possible use case scenarios.....	12
4 User requirements and customer values.....	12
4.1 High level strategy addressing the societal and business pain.....	12
4.2 General description of requirements.....	13
4.3 Core customer values.....	15
4.4 I-SEAMORE exploitation models.....	16
5 The Market.....	17
5.1 Market segmentation.....	17
5.2 Market potential for the use case scenario preventing illegal immigration.....	18
5.3 Market potential for the use case scenario preventing drug smuggling.....	19
5.4 Market entry barriers.....	21
6 Competition.....	24
6.1 Competition for the use case scenario preventing illegal immigration.....	24
6.2 Competition for the use case scenario preventing drug smuggling.....	25
6.3 Competitive advantages and unique selling propositions.....	26
7 Marketing, sales and distribution.....	28
7.1 Distribution and sales strategy.....	29
7.2 Communication and PR strategy.....	31
8 Conclusions.....	32
References.....	34
List of Acronyms.....	35
List of Tables.....	36
List of figures.....	36

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope

I-SEAMORE is an ecosystem composed of an advanced platform solution to host and manage the operation of several innovative assets, services and systems that aim to provide European authorities with increased situational awareness and operational capabilities for maritime surveillance resorting to aerial and water surface support.

The core platform (infrastructure and software layers) is developed to be operated at Maritime Operation Centres (MOCs) with interfaces to other systems including UxVs Ground Control Stations (GCSs), as well as at external systems, e.g., such as rescue management centres. It thus provides end-users with a holistic platform capable of handling several multipurpose tasks such as wide maritime border and coastal areas monitoring, analysis of potential threats, support to search and rescue operations, detection of illegal activities, among others. Such tasks will be possible since the I-SEAMORE platform provides a complete set of functionalities and capabilities to mission commanders, focusing on four main pillars:

1. Employment and indirect tasking of multiple types of long-endurance unmanned assets (aerial and water surface),
2. Exploitation of heterogeneous data sources, e.g., payload data, earth observation data and open data sources including Copernicus Services,
3. Provision of a common operational picture empowered by a novel and comprehensive suite of data fusion services based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data analysis, for optimal decision making and successful mission execution of the desired missions, and
4. Interoperability within the ecosystem and its interface with key existing external systems.

Moreover, the I-SEAMORE development activities also unlock the potential for an uptake of the solution at EU level, as well as multi-country, multi-authority collaboration, including novel concepts of operation, standard operating procedures for joint operations, and new methodologies for co-creation and validation of maritime situational awareness and maritime security solutions by end-users.

Within this publication, we describe the business development approach towards commercialization strategy building. Based on the stakeholder analysis and based on a detailed description of multiple stakeholder groups, the interactions and value streams especially between I-SEAMORE and maritime authorities were drawn, and exploitation models were developed. This general business model design is complemented by analysis of target markets, market entry barriers and elements of a commercialization strategy. Consequently, this document lays the ground for future exploitation and application of I-SEAMORE systems, products, and services.

1.2 Synopsis and methods of our approach

In line with the goals of the I-SEAMORE project, our approach covers several topics that I-SEAMORE must explore for its successful market take-up: Our starting point was to focus on Maritime Authorities as key stakeholders and potential customers (in chapter 2). The core of the technical architecture and the referring use cases are documented in chapter 3. In chapter 4, we look at the user requirements, and at the core customer values impacted by I-SEAMORE as well as at the resulting value propositions and exploitation models. In the then following chapter 5, we provide an overview on the market potential referring to the identified core customer groups Maritime Authorities, including the view on market entry barriers, and complemented by looking at competition (in chapter 6). This leads to the consideration of marketing and sales strategies in chapter 7.

The analysis work is built on a combination of different analytic methods and analytical tools like literature review and secondary data analysis. It is used as a part of trend scanning process, structured around themes and related theories. Moreover, for the use cases and application scenarios considered in the I-

SEAMORE project, appropriate examples were sought via desk research, and lessons learned were generated.

In addition, interviews with project partners were conducted, and information about the user requirements for the understanding of impacted values for the described use cases were retrieved and are taken into consideration. The partner interview sessions were complemented by external stakeholders' panels. Especially, the so-called end users as project partners contributed to the analytical part as well, combined their knowledge and provided "insider" expertise.

© Rafael Ben Ari, Dreamstime.com (ID 31951508)

2 STAKEHOLDER FOCUS

A stakeholder is a person or entity involved (having a ‘stake’) in I-SEAMORE products and/or services. Stakeholder segmentation is the process of dividing a broad value consumer or value provider community into sub-groups of stakeholders (known as segments) based on some type of shared characteristics. Stakeholder segmentation is critical for the business planning and the implementation of the exploitation strategies. Therefore, the relations of the participating entities are described in the following overview:

Stakeholder groups	ID	Key stakeholder	Primary stakeholder	Secondary stakeholder
Government	G	Border authorities Law enforcement agencies Governmental agencies	Environment protection agencies Traffic/Port authorities Public funding provider EC and nationally funded projects	Regulators, certifiers, standardisation bodies Incubators, venture builders Accelerators
Business	B	Industry (Corporates, SMEs, Startups)	Farmers and agriculture companies Insurance companies Hunting and fishing clubs	Financiers (investors) Tourism stakeholders
NGOs	N	Humanitarian bodies	Environment protection agencies Certifying organisations Standardisation bodies	Associations & lobbying groups Incubators, venture builders Accelerators
Academia	A	Universities RTOs		
Leveraging groups	L			Influencers, newsmakers
Individual consumers	C		Civil society	

FIGURE 1: KEY STAKEHOLDERS IN THE VALUE-GENERATION CHAIN IN THE SURVEILLANCE MARKET¹

The I-SEAMORE project is a forward-thinking initiative. Consequently, for addressing different possible commercialization and exploitation channels, it is also crucial to take a forward-thinking approach: understanding that, in addition to law enforcement agencies, border security and other governmental authorities, there is a variety of stakeholders potentially interested to ensure successful exploitation, uptake, and long-term sustainable application of the project results.

In Figure 1 above, we divide all identified potential stakeholders into two main groups with related subgroups to provide a categorization for the benefit of a better stakeholder overview:

- According to the influence and impact the I-SEAMORE project generates:
 - Key Stakeholder (High impact, high efficiency, international influence)
 - Primary Stakeholder (Middle impact, middle efficiency, national influence)
 - Secondary Stakeholder (Low impact, low efficiency, regional influence)
- According to their role in the value generation chain:
 - Government (G) = a state institution in maritime and border surveillance sector
 - Business (B) = companies as input providers for consumer/costumer all along the value generation chain
 - NGOs (N) = non-governmental Organizations (Humanitarian Bodies, etc.)
 - Academia (A) = research Institutions (Universities, RTOs)
 - Levering groups (L) = groups like Influencers, manipulators, etc.
 - Individual consumers (C) = general Public

Thereby, the most important key stakeholders are the Border Authorities, Law Enforcement Agencies and policy makers, which belong to the Government group. These are the individuals that purchase and use the I-SEAMORE system in the future and thus play a major role. While the I-SEAMORE platform offers numerous

¹ © INI-Novation GmbH

use cases considered in the I-SEAMORE project² applying for Border Authorities and Law Enforcement Agencies, hereinafter collectively referred to as **“Maritime Authorities”**, the platform also has the potential to address the technology challenges of the other key stakeholder groups:

It is obvious that the vast technological capabilities to monitor the water and coastal areas of multiple countries, and to analyse the data stemming from various assets and sources, will empower **public and private stakeholders involved in wide area surveillance** to take initiatives that improve the quality of life of communities, provide new business opportunities, or even ensure the preservation of the biodiversity and endangered species.

Similarly, **private and public rescue organisations** (i.e., Mare Accident Investigation Board – MAIB, Search and Rescue – SAR), as well as many other **private and public humanitarian bodies with rescue missions** play an important role in the success of the I-SEAMORE project. By contributing to the project via technology advancements, market opportunities or aligning project goals with societal needs, they can leverage the technical architecture of I-SEAMORE into different applications.

Also, **private companies such as security contractors, shipping companies, as well as port authorities** may benefit from enhanced surveillance systems to secure maritime routes and assets. The growing need for monitoring in busy international shipping lanes, exclusive economic zones (EEZs), and maritime borders creates a strong demand for such systems.

Furthermore, **stakeholders in maritime data spaces** will be considered as future consumers of I-SEAMORE services and data, because data cooperation may put I-SEAMORE users in the position as data providers or data consumers, which will open them opportunities to gain benefits such as revenues or costs savings through data cooperation means.

The primary value that the I-SEAMORE system offers in the considered scenarios is enhanced situational awareness capabilities, enabling the detection of potential human trafficking activities, and providing support for search and rescue operations. The I-SEAMORE consortium already addresses requirements of the here considered main stakeholder “Maritime Authorities”, defence and border agencies, and coast guards who need advanced maritime surveillance solutions. Within this category “Maritime Authorities” we also consider organizations such as NATO, EUROMARFOR, EMSA as potential customers, because they will also benefit from enhanced situational awareness capabilities and decision support. Consequently, in the following chapters this publication focuses on the business modelling elaborations for this key stakeholder group.

3 I-SEAMORE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND USE CASES

3.1 System description

The I-SEAMORE ecosystem is a common and innovative environment for the simultaneous and cooperative deployment and operation of various technologies for maritime surveillance. Such technologies could be unmanned aerial and water surface assets, data fusion mechanisms, services, and tools, as well as the entire infrastructure required for computation and communication. The primary objective of I-SEAMORE is to bolster European authorities' situational awareness and operational capacities in the realm of maritime surveillance operations.

The I-SEAMORE ecosystem uses innovative state of the art components for a common environment to allow for the simultaneous and cooperative deployment and operation of various technologies for maritime surveillance. By ensuring the open and scalable design of the I-SEAMORE platform from the beginning, the consortium partners developed a complete platform with advanced maritime surveillance capabilities. The I-SEAMORE platform focusses primarily on four key areas, which are considered fundamental for the requirements and technology challenges of potential customers, and which will be fundamental for introducing more advanced applications at a later stage. The four key areas are:

- Operating unmanned assets for continuous maritime surveillance, including long-endurance aerial and water surface platforms;

² They are described below in sub-chapter 3.2

- Using heterogeneous data sources through innovative sensor payloads and open data sources, including Copernicus-based services;
- Enabling shared situational awareness and operational pictures, empowered by novel and comprehensive suite of data fusion services, based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data Analysis; and
- Ensuring the interoperability within the Ecosystem and its interface with key external systems using a Common Information Sharing Environment (CISE).

The central platform, encompassing both infrastructure and software components, is envisioned to be deployed and managed at Maritime Operations Centers (MOCs). These MOCs are equipped with interfaces to interconnect with other systems, including Ground Control Stations (GCSs) for Unmanned Vehicles (UxVs). The platform offers end-users a comprehensive solution capable of performing a multitude of versatile tasks. These tasks encompass extensive monitoring of maritime borders and coastal areas, analysis of potential threats, support for search and rescue operations, and the detection of illicit activities, among other functions. Figure 1 below illustrates the High-Level Architecture of the I-SEAMORE ecosystem:

FIGURE 2: ARCHITECTURE OF THE I-SEAMORE ECOSYSTEM³

The core of the I-SEAMORE ecosystem of technologies is the I-SEAMORE Operation Platform, which facilitates the automation of operation cycles, orchestrating various systems and assets in use, including the network and data centres infrastructure. Its modular and extendable nature allows for a smoother and faster integration of supplementary assets, data, or tools within the I-SEAMORE Ecosystem, thus enabling the scalability of the platform and advancing the creation of a collaborative and facilitating environment to support future operations conducted by multiple authorities. The pivotal feature of the I-SEAMORE platform is its software layers, which incorporate a range of dedicated services and tools. These elements grant a mission commander access to a complete array of capabilities, including, for instance, the provision of a shared operational picture. The architecture encompasses a range of components, i.e.

- Data fusion applications that extract valuable insights from the collected data;
- I-SEAMORE's structural services that ensure data persistence and secure on-demand communication; as well as
- Applications and services that leverage these resources to deliver the essential functionalities required by end users.

³ © The I-SEAMORE consortium

These functionalities represent benefits granted by I-SEAMORE to end users, achieved through the integration of cutting-edge sensing technologies and AI-driven data processing, enabling advanced services for border monitoring. Within this framework, the platform assumes a pivotal role by harnessing automation to facilitate the timely deployment of the entire systems or its components, making them readily available on demand. Thereby, the core focus is put on the use cases briefly described in the sub-chapters below.

3.2 Use cases

The use cases identified within the project are related to two complex and multifaceted issues that affect the European territory: irregular immigration and drug smuggling. Both challenges require enhanced collaboration among authorities, improvements in data/information sharing and data elaboration, especially in relation to maritime surveillance. In this sense, the setting up of practical scenarios would help in evaluating the efficacy and effectiveness of I-SEAMORE solutions vis-à-vis these challenges.

3.2.1 Detecting unauthorized border crossing:

According to FRONTEX, there has been a significant surge in irregular border crossings, particularly within the European Maritime Space [1]. These occurrences are predominantly associated with irregular migration and often result in tragic outcomes. Regrettably, between 2014 and 2018, more than 12,000 people drowned and were never found. In 2023, 3,155 migrants died while crossing the Mediterranean Sea. As of January 2025, 2,333 casualties were recorded [2]. These data emphasizes that these routes represent some of the most perilous maritime migration routes globally, underscoring the imperative for Maritime Authorities to proactively enhance their detection and response capabilities in such incidents.

FIGURE 3: NUMBER OF RECORDED DEATHS OF MIGRANTS IN THE MEDITERRANEAN SEA 2014 TO 2024⁴

Exploiting the political instability in certain departure countries, organized crime groups have capitalized on the opportunity to facilitate the smuggling of migrants across EU borders. This alarming trend necessitates proactive cooperation among states to bolster detection and response capabilities. The urgency to address this issue has prompted a collective call for enhanced collaboration and concerted efforts to tackle the challenges posed by unauthorized border crossings.

In this use case, the primary focus is on the detection of unauthorized border crossings and propose strategies to mitigate this pressing issue. Leveraging advanced technologies, data analysis, and improved cooperation mechanisms, enhances the capabilities of border authorities in promptly identifying and responding to such activities. Consequently, the goal of the I-SEAMORE project is to demonstrate an efficient and proactive framework that strengthens border security and ensures the integrity of EU borders in the face of evolving threats posed by organized crime groups.

⁴ © Statista [2]

This specific I-SEAMORE use case considers a scenario wherein a vessel carrying migrants attempts to reach the European coast while intentionally avoiding the reporting of AIS (Automatic Identification System) signals to evade detection. The situation unfolds during the early hours of the morning, characterized by foggy conditions and low sunlight. Within this challenging environment, the primary objective is to apply advanced technologies that enable the timely detection and interception of the migrant vessel present in the I-SEAMORE system. By leveraging sophisticated surveillance systems, such as radar and thermal imaging, combined with data analytics and pattern recognition algorithms, the capabilities of border authorities get enhanced to identify and track vessels engaged in irregular migration. Given the foggy conditions and limited visibility caused by low sunlight, the use case emphasizes the need for specialized sensors and enhanced situational awareness tools. By integrating weather data, real-time environmental monitoring, and advanced imaging technologies, authorities can optimize their detection capabilities and effectively counter the efforts of migrants attempting to exploit these conditions for covert entry. The safety of both migrants and the communities involved gets assured while upholding the integrity of border control measures. The I-SEAMORE system's novel services perform a comprehensive assessment of the situation. The following table summarizes the main aspects of this use case:

Use Case Summary: Preventing Irregular Migration	
Issue in a nutshell	Irregular migration across EU borders has surged recently, indicating a growing concern and the need for proactive measures to detect and mitigate unauthorized border crossings, exploited by organized crime groups.
I-SEAMORE objective	Detection of unauthorized border crossings and enhancement of timely response by operators, by leveraging advanced technologies, data analysis, and improved cooperation mechanisms.
I-SEAMORE use case scenario	The use case focuses on detecting irregular migration near the maritime borders of Spain and/or Portugal. It involves a scenario where a migrant vessel attempts to evade detection by not reporting AIS signals, exploiting foggy conditions and low sunlight. Advanced technologies like radar, thermal imaging, data analytics, and pattern recognition algorithms are employed to enhance border authorities' capabilities in identifying and intercepting such vessels. Specialized sensors and situational awareness tools are crucial in optimizing detection in challenging maritime environments.
I-SEAMORE tested solution	A drone detects RF signals indicating the presence of humans in a suspicious maritime corridor, and the application confirms the vessel as carrying migrants, triggering an alert. As the MOC performs a comprehensive assessment of the situation, the Mission Commander directs the UAV to lower altitude for monitoring, combining the activity with EO data analysis and coordinates interception efforts with relevant authorities.
Customer value	Advanced technologies ensure effective detection and response to irregular migration, safeguarding both migrants and communities while upholding border control integrity.

TABLE 1: USE CASE NO 1: PREVENTING IRREGULAR MIGRATION

3.2.2 Preventing smuggling of drugs

According to Giordana Aragno [3] the European Union has been actively promoting collaborative efforts among member states to combat the issue of illicit drug trafficking. The primary objective of this cooperation is to suppress illicit drug trafficking by sea through the enhancement of criminal intelligence and coordinated police action in international waters. To achieve this goal, several measures are being implemented, including improved monitoring of ship movements and equipment within harbours, increased storage, sharing, and analysis of data collection, and a better understanding of the drug market, including estimations and demands.

One notable case scenario involves the transportation of narcotics by sea from Morocco to Europe, which has seen an increase in recent years. This route has been the focus of seizures off the coast of North Africa, with suspicions that some of the drugs were destined for Europe.

Current challenges faced by the end-users:

1. Obtaining early-warning for vessels exhibiting suspicious behaviour, particularly in remote maritime areas where detection is becoming increasingly difficult.
2. Enhancing cooperation and coordination in the utilization of UxVs to improve data collection and dissemination, all aimed towards a common goal;
3. Improving the technology systems employed as UxV payloads, thereby enhancing capabilities in scenarios characterized by low visibility or nocturnal conditions.

The primary objective of this use case is to validate the I-SEAMORE solution, which involves the fusion of heterogeneous vessel information. The scenario also involves the integration of diverse data sources such as UxVs' payload data, coastal surveillance radar data, AIS, satellite imagery provided by Copernicus services, and other relevant open-source data. The following table summarizes the main aspects of this use case:

Use Case Summary: Preventing Smuggling of Drugs	
Issue in a nutshell	The European Union is actively combating illicit drug trafficking by sea, aiming to enhance criminal intelligence and coordinated police action in international waters. FRONTEX analysis result show a significant increase in drug smuggling incidents in 2022 compared with 2021. This increase confirms the persistent trend in the growth in drug supply, significantly exceeding the demand in the European drug market [4].
I-SEAMORE objective	Fusion of heterogeneous vessel information in to detect anomalies, risks, and threats associated with the smuggling of illicit goods through persistent surveillance methods. This will address the main challenges nowadays faced by end-users, namely: a) obtaining early-warning for suspicious vessels; b) enhancing cooperation and coordination in the utilization of UxVs; and c) improving the technology system installed on UxVs, especially those related with potentiated operability in nocturnal and low visibility conditions.
I-SEAMORE use case scenario	The scenario involves the smuggling of narcotics from Morocco to Europe, focusing on night-time illicit activities with small, fast boats interacting with merchant vessels.
I-SEAMORE tested solution	The I-SEAMORE solution responds to suspicious behaviour by initiating coordinated actions. It analyses AIS data to identify a merchant vessel deviating from its route, triggering a suspicious activity alert for the Mission Commander. UAVs are deployed to survey the area and detect a smaller boat approaching the vessel. Additional UAVs and USVs collaborate to monitor the event, providing data for identifying illicit cargo. Manned means are activated for interdiction and seamlessly transferring control to authorities if needed.
Customer value	This cooperative approach ensures an effective response, enabling uninterrupted monitoring and tracking across jurisdictional boundaries.

TABLE 2. USE CASE NO 2: PREVENTING SMUGGLING OF DRUGS

The use case aims to detect anomalies, risks, and threats associated with the smuggling of illicit goods through persistent surveillance methods. Additionally, it aims to optimize the utilization of available resources and assets for mitigation and interdiction operations. Special attention was given to information sharing and cooperation between adjacent member states, specifically Portugal and Spain within the context of this scenario.

3.2.3 Other possible use case scenarios

The primary value that the I-SEAMORE system offers in the considered scenarios is enhanced situational awareness capabilities, enabling the detection of potential human trafficking activities and providing support for search and rescue operations. For instance, smugglers often employ small boats for trafficking, and I-SEAMORE's solution offers early detection and monitoring capabilities for potential human trafficking activity through its innovative services, including detecting and identifying uncooperative vessels, identifying electromagnetic signals (e.g., cell phone signals) to pinpoint traffickers, and actively assisting in search and rescue operations for migrants.

Such application is one of the many similar applications in the I-SEAMORE maritime border protection domain. Many other use case scenarios would demonstrate the benefits of the I-SEAMORE system, and its components as illustrated in figure 4 below:

FIGURE 4: POSSIBLE I-SEAMORE USE CASES⁵

4 USER REQUIREMENTS AND CUSTOMER VALUES

I-SEAMORE offers end-users a comprehensive solution capable of performing a multitude of versatile tasks. These tasks encompass extensive monitoring of maritime borders and coastal areas, analysis of potential threats, support for search and rescue operations, and the detection of illicit activities, among other functions. The interfaces incorporate user authentication and authorization features, providing different portals and functionalities tailored to various teams, all built on a foundation of secure communication. To capture the value generated for Maritime Authorities in the described use cases not only the customers' challenges, but also their specific requirements must be considered. By responding to the different requirements, the I-SEAMORE system can address specific solutions, which can impact customer values.

4.1 High level strategy addressing the societal and business pain

As illustrated, I-SEAMORE is designed to cater for a range of different challenges and needs, especially of its key target customers. By including the offering of I-SEAMORE solutions within their core portfolio of products and services, the business activities of I-SEAMORE partners can be extended with new services providing solutions to cater customers' needs, even beyond those addressed within this document. The initial

⁵ © ATOS/Eviden

conclusion for responding to target customers' challenges can be formulated into the following high-level strategic positioning:

The I-SEAMORE system focusses on enhanced situational awareness in the growing maritime surveillance market. The demand for secure, reliable, interoperable, and automated surveillance solutions, particularly in Europe, provides a fertile ground for the platform's growth, with additional opportunities for expansion into global markets and partnerships. The use of cutting-edge technologies and alignment with EU policy frameworks strengthens its competitive standing in the evolving landscape of innovative security solutions.

Consequently, the I-SEAMORE commercial exploitation will require a diverse partnership network to sustain and expand its services. These partnerships should ensure technological innovation, regulatory compliance, financial stability, industry adoption, and continuous development, making the exploitation of I-SEAMORE results a long-term success in target customer sectors.

As illustrated above, the I-SEAMORE systems and services will provide innovation in the chosen markets not only on technological but as well on a social level. Through a dedicated family of innovative components (engineered and prototyped with feedback from users and stakeholders during the development), I-SEAMORE partners formulated their mission of becoming leading providers of a portfolio of solutions and exceed expectations of its stakeholders by:

- Harnessing the power of a growing global network of innovative technology companies, on-going further development efforts, and committed public and private stakeholders;
- Leveraging existing breakthrough technologies, applications and services; and
- Unlocking the true competitive power of the developed technical architecture.

I-SEAMORE partners are committed and will always strive to be highly regarded organizations recognized for their ethical standards and products/services of exceptional value.

4.2 General description of requirements

As a result of co-creation workshops (conducted during the project with participation of technology providers and system users), functionality expectations were drawn, divided into AI-technology requirements, UXV-technology requirements, and data integration/data fusion requirements. These functional requirements can be summarized as follows⁶:

- **Automated identification and tracking of vessels:** The system shall allow the automated classification of vessels, verify the correctness of the information gathered and calculate the degree of risk / interest of the vessels. This function will also allow validations, if identified routes of vessels can be considered suspicious.
- **CISE Connector Module:** The CISE connector facilitates the exchange of information between different surveillance systems by sharing data such as vessel positions or trajectories. It provides information in real-time enhancing the situational awareness and improving the coordination of maritime surveillance across different organizations and borders.
- **Debriefing tool:** This tool supports analysing and understanding data collected during surveillance operations, impacting the ability to annotate and visualize acquired and processed data to identify trends, patterns, and anomalies.
- **Visualization tool:** With the visualization tool data can be better understood and interpreted. The tools may include maps, charts, other graphical representations of data, allowing a visually supported overview of vessel movements, patterns, and behaviour.

⁶ A very detailed analysis of technical requirements - divided into AI-technology requirements, UXV-technology requirements, and data integration/data fusion requirements - can be found in the publicly available document: Deliverable D8.3, Chapter 5.3 "User requirements in the value generation chain" [5]

- **Annotation tool:** Annotations can be used to add context and insights to the data such as highlighting specific vessels or areas of interest, marking unusual events or behaviours, and notifying incidents. Consequently, analysts are supported to quickly access and review relevant information.

Functionalities that can meet these requirements enable target customer values provided by I-SEAMORE. The focus on user-centric design and proactive risk mitigation is also commendable, as it not only improves operational efficiency but also addresses societal and ethical considerations through its comprehensive ethical framework, which leads to the highly innovative outcomes of the I-SEAMORE system:

Enhanced Maritime Surveillance and Border Security

- Improved monitoring of maritime borders through AI-powered situational awareness.
- Automatic anomaly detection reduces reliance on individual operator expertise, increasing consistency and accuracy.
- Data fusion from multiple sources enables early warning and improved tracking of illegal activities.
- Real-time operational management and advanced decision-making tools optimize resource utilization.

Interoperability and Multi-Platform Integration

- Seamless integration with existing maritime surveillance systems and assets.
- A platform capable of incorporating data from various airborne and surface assets.
- Utilization of CISE data models ensures interoperability across European surveillance networks.
- A unique “system of systems” approach, combining legacy coastal surveillance with unmanned assets and advanced data fusion services.

AI and Data Fusion for Advanced Analytics

- AI-driven decision support enhances detection accuracy and threat anticipation.
- Application of Hybrid Transfer Learning for maritime surveillance in large-scale EU systems.
- Statistical models allow efficient incorporation of legacy AI-based components and new assets.
- Advanced interfacing principles enable smooth integration of fusion functions at multiple levels.

Ethical, Legal, and Societal Considerations

- A comprehensive ethical framework ensures that social, legal, and privacy concerns guide project development.
- Engagement with NGOs, CSOs, and the public through surveys and participatory workshops promotes societal acceptance.
- Compliance with the EU AI Act, integrating principles of fairness, transparency, and human oversight.
- Use of the ALTAI framework for trustworthy AI assessment and external ethics expert collaboration.

Operational Efficiency and Cost-Effectiveness

- Common command and control capabilities optimize maritime surveillance operations.
- Sustainability-focused approach with optimized resource usage and cost-efficient solutions.
- End-to-end capabilities, from training and evaluation of concepts of operations (ConOps) to real-time execution.

Thereby, the customer challenges that can be tackled by the I-SEAMORE solutions are many-fold and can be summarised into the following categories:

- Technological Challenges
- Data Integration & Interoperability Challenges
- Operational & Decision-Making Challenges
- Security, Data Privacy & Threat Mitigation Challenges
- Regulatory Challenges
- Financial Challenges

The emphasis on responding to challenges of diverse stakeholder groups and aligning with trustworthy AI principles reflects a forward-thinking approach to ensuring both effectiveness and ethical compliance in maritime operations. It seems like I-SEAMORE is not just about technological advancement but also about a solution that is socially accepted and aligned with human rights, which is crucial for such sensitive

domains. All features of the I-SEAMORE architecture represent potential solutions for linking market demand and technological capability. For example, many of the value proposition respond to the fragmentation of stakeholder preferences and requirements and the resultant demand for more diverse and personalized offerings. Personalization has been made possible by the different elements of the architecture and turned into services, such as decision support services, recommendations, and alerts, which may be different for each group of customers/users. Therefore, I-SEAMORE has been specifically designed to be scalable and upgradeable across the whole spectrum of various needs of many different stakeholders and potential customers. The I-SEAMORE service delivery model with the hardware, software and data-integration services is a comprehensive straight solution. In comparison to other providers, it is an all-in-one solution, which means a free flow of data, information, and knowledge directly to the point where it is needed. These circumstances can be turned into a set of customer values, enabling many possible exploitations models.

4.3 Core customer values

Responding to the circumstance that the I-SEAMORE core customer values are manyfold, we created, by applying the Value Proposition Canvas [6] compelling value propositions that resonate with the expectations of Maritime Authorities as target customers. Based on the outcome of that analysis, providers of the I-SEAMORE system, hardware, software, and services can differentiate the offerings in the market, and drive customer acquisition and satisfaction. Thereby it is obvious that it is not just one specific functionality driving the customer values. It is the combination of existing technologies in a single platform with layered approach that provides modularity through abstraction, resulting in proper responses to the key customers' challenges. In summary, dedicated services solve operational challenges, which are faced by potential customers in their daily operations. Those challenges and the corresponding values impacted by I-SEAMORE summarised in the following table:

I-SEAMORE's customer values for Maritime Authorities	
Key challenges	Customer Values
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited resources and manpower to monitor vast border areas effectively • High risk of missing or overlooking illegal immigration due to manual surveillance • Complex methods used by illegal immigrants to evade detection • Smugglers constantly changing tactics to avoid detection • Increased human traffic makes border surveillance more difficult • Need for detection of concrete quantity of people in a boat • Problems in finding vessels operating in the dark (poor evidence rate) • Manual processes leading to potential errors in identifying threats • Lack of advanced mission planning • Lack of early detection capabilities • Lack of long-range detection • Lack of detection algorithms modifiable by the authorities as end users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced ability to detect and prevent illegal activities with advanced technologies • Real-time intelligence and data insights for proactive decision-making • Identification of vessels and behaviour context: increased ability to detect uncooperative targets and intercept illegal attempts • Automation of surveillance with increase efficiency: reducing the need for manual monitoring through automated systems, minimizing the risk of oversight • Enabling of persistent and continuous surveillance as well as recording information gathered • Streamlined and efficient border control processes (reduced number of border crossings) • Accurate Intelligence: Reliable, timely intelligence for proactive measures • Improved coordination and information sharing with other agencies • Better compliance with regulations and more accurate reporting • Lower operational costs

TABLE 3: OVERVIEW ON KEY CUSTOMER VALUES FOR MARITIME AUTHORITIES

In conclusion, I-SEAMORE's value creation and value delivery is not only achieved from the pure technical point of view. Moreover, the I-SEAMORE core system is complemented by the regulatory ethical and trusted framework, which includes fundamental European principles such as sovereignty, fairness, ethics, security, and trust. The applying situational awareness technologies reduce the risk of undetected maritime threats or incidents, not only for maritime authorities. They are also detecting risks and lowering risk exposure for many different stakeholders. This will also in the future lead to continuous improvement and adaptation of surveillance technologies to meet evolving maritime threats.

4.4 I-SEAMORE exploitation models

For those core customer values we derived different exploitation models. They can be approached from several angles depending on the technology's capabilities and the primary use cases. For this purpose, the referring value proposition for Maritime Authorities can be summarised as follows:

- Enhanced situational awareness;
- Detection of uncooperative targets;
- Electromagnetic signal identification;
- Prolonged operation of aerial assets;
- Coordination of multi-domain assets for search and rescue support;
- Early detection and monitoring of maritime threats such as drug smuggling or human trafficking activities;
- Efficient surveillance and response to drug smuggling and human trafficking, alongside maritime safety improvements; and
- Single point of view for detailed information and multiple data sources (integrated playback of all mission data).

All features of the I-SEAMORE architecture represent potential solutions for linking market demand and technological capability. Many of the value proposition respond to the fragmentation of different stakeholder preferences and requirements as well as to the resultant demand for more diverse and personalized offerings. Personalization has been made possible by the different elements of the architecture. It can be turned into services, such as decision support services, recommendations, and alerts, which may be different for each group of customers/users. Therefore, I-SEAMORE has been specifically designed to be scalable and upgradeable across the whole spectrum of various needs of many different stakeholders and potential customers. Exploitation and payment models need to be adjusted consequently, shifting towards service delivery fees, time fees (typically quarterly recurring compensation) plus maintenance/upgrade schemas.

In each of the exploitation models, the key focus is on leveraging the specific value propositions that I-SEAMORE maritime surveillance technologies offer, whether through direct sales, service models, licensing, or partnerships. This approach ensures that the technology can be adapted to various markets and stakeholders, including both public and private entities, while addressing pressing needs in maritime security and safety. The I-SEAMORE service delivery and exploitation models with the hardware, software and data-integration services are a comprehensive straight solution. In comparison to other providers, it is an all-in-one solution, which means a free flow of data, information, and knowledge directly to the point where it is needed.

There are some common exploitation models tailored to Maritime Authorities as target customers in accordance with their typical value propositions. These models vary depending on the specific values offered by the solution. Examples are summarised below:

I-SEAMORE's exploitation models in accordance with values impacted for Maritime Authorities	
Value Proposition	Exploitation Model
Enhanced situational awareness, detection of uncooperative targets, prolonged operation of aerial assets, and coordination of multi-domain assets for search and rescue (SAR).	Secure direct contracts with maritime border authorities (e.g., FRONTEX, national coast guards) for technology deployment. This could involve ongoing subscription-based models where surveillance technology is provided as a service, continuously monitoring maritime activities, and enhancing search-and-rescue operations. Government contracts offer long-term revenue streams and stability.
Detection of uncooperative vessels, electromagnetic signal identification, and search-and-rescue support.	Licensing agreements with customers paying for licenses to use the technology or acquire proprietary hardware with integrated software. Additional service fees could be added for ongoing technical support or software updates.
Efficient surveillance and response to drug smuggling and human trafficking, alongside maritime safety improvements.	Collaborate with governments to form PPPs where the technology is deployed in exchange for co-financing from both public agencies and private sector entities. This could reduce upfront costs for governments while still enabling the deployment of necessary technologies.
Real-time data for detecting suspicious maritime activities, including human trafficking or drug smuggling.	Offer data as a service (DaaS) by selling real-time monitoring data, historical analytics, or reports. The clients would subscribe to the data feeds on a recurring basis, paying for data access according to specific regions or timeframes of interest.
Continuous improvement and adaptation of surveillance technologies to meet evolving maritime threats.	Participate in co-funded research projects (e.g., Horizon Europe) to further develop the technology in collaboration with other stakeholders like research institutions, technology firms, technology integrators, and national security bodies. This could provide access to additional R&D funding while ensuring that the technology remains at the forefront of maritime surveillance innovation.

TABLE 4: KEY CUSTOMER VALUES AND REFERRING EXPLOITATION MODELS

5 THE MARKET

5.1 Market segmentation

The global maritime surveillance market is growing steadily due to increasing security concerns, irregular migration, and evolving maritime threats such as smuggling and human trafficking. This market is expected to see continued expansion driven by technological advancements in surveillance, tracking, and AI-driven monitoring systems. According to reports, the maritime surveillance market as a whole is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 3.2% from 2023 to 2028, with a focus on improving safety, security, and situational awareness in coastal and border areas [7]. The demand for such solutions is being driven by the increasing complexity of illegal immigration routes, especially in Europe and North America. Investments in surveillance infrastructure by governments and private sectors are also contributing to this market's growth [7].

In the following, we provide an overview on the target markets and demand structures for the key target customer groups "Maritime Authorities" for the use case "preventing illegal immigration" (in sub-chapter 5.2) and for the use case "preventing illegal drug smuggling" (in sub-chapter 5.3). For each of the thus

determined market segments we apply the so-called “TAM, SAM, SOM” consideration to describe the market potential. “TAM – SAM – SOM” is a method of systematizing and making transparent the market assessment in money or units for business planning purposes. The procedure is increasingly used for market launches or in the context of budgeting. The following terms are used hereinafter:

- TAM – Total Addressable Market / Total Available Market
- SAM – Serviceable Available Market / Served Available Market
- SOM – Serviceable Obtainable Market / Share of Market

5.2 Market potential for the use case scenario preventing illegal immigration

To assess the Total Addressable Market (TAM), Serviceable Available Market (SAM), and Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM) for exploiting maritime surveillance technologies we considered several factors related to the global demand for these technologies, especially for applications like preventing illegal immigration and enhancing border security. Thereby, specifically for applications like border control, illegal immigration prevention, and maritime security within Europe, we considered both the current state of the European market and the technologies applicable to the region. Here is a breakdown, which provides a strategic outlook on market entry and exploitation potential for maritime surveillance technologies. Within Europe the focus is on high-demand areas such as the Mediterranean, along with cooperation with EU agencies like Frontex and European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA), will be key to realizing market potential:

TAM, SAM and SOM for the customer group “Maritime Authorities” Use case scenario “preventing illegal immigration”	
<p>Total Addressable Market (TAM):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • \$33 billion worldwide • \$8-10 billion in Europe 	<p>TAM refers to the overall global market demand for maritime surveillance technologies without any limitations. For the maritime surveillance market, especially with illegal immigration prevention and border control being key applications, TAM includes all potential global markets where these technologies can be used.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The global maritime surveillance market is expected to reach \$33 billion by 2028, growing at a CAGR of 3.2% from 2023 to 2028 [7]. • The TAM would account for all possible maritime surveillance systems (e.g., radar, satellite, drones, AI-based systems) used by border security agencies, coast guards, and naval forces across continents. <p>The estimated TAM for maritime surveillance in Europe, based on global market projections and Europe's share in global defence/security spending, is around \$8-10 billion (approx. 25-30% of the global market) [8] Europe is home to strong technological capabilities and regulatory frameworks such as FRONTEX, EMSA and Copernicus programs that support maritime surveillance.</p>
<p>Serviceable Available Market (SAM):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • \$10-12 billion worldwide • \$5-6 billion in Europe 	<p>SAM refers to the portion of the TAM that can realistically be targeted at about 30% of the worldwide market, considering regulatory environments, existing technological ecosystems, and governmental priorities for maritime security.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FRONTEX, the European Border and Coast Guard Agency, and other national maritime authorities have increased funding and interest in maritime surveillance technologies to protect EU maritime borders. • The SAM in Europe would focus primarily on Mediterranean countries, where most irregular immigration and maritime crime take place, as well as on Northern European countries.

TAM, SAM and SOM for the customer group "Maritime Authorities" Use case scenario "preventing illegal immigration"	
Serviceable Available Market (continued):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other countries like Germany, France, and Scandinavia also contribute significantly to demand for advanced surveillance systems to monitor cargo and protect territorial waters. <p>Based on the focus of funding and initiatives like Copernicus Maritime Surveillance Service and the EMSA, the SAM is estimated to be \$5-6 billion across Europe, as it targets governmental and institutional buyers [8].</p>
Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Up to \$1,2 billion worldwide \$300 million to \$600 million in Europe 	<p>SOM is the share of the SAM that the company or organization can realistically capture, considering competition, partnerships, and resources.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SOM could be calculated based on current market penetration in target regions. For a European-based maritime surveillance technology provider, capturing 5-10% of the SAM globally would be a realistic target in the next few years [9]. <p>For instance, for a market of \$12 billion (SAM), the obtainable market (SOM) might be \$600 million to \$1.2 billion, depending on competitive advantages and successful deployment of innovative solutions.</p>

TABLE 5: TAM, SAM, SOM FOR THE USE CASE SCENARIO "PREVENTING ILLEGAL IMMIGRATION"

5.3 Market potential for the use case scenario preventing drug smuggling

The maritime surveillance market for the prevention of illegal drug smuggling is a significant and growing sector, driven by increasing global efforts to combat organized crime, drug trafficking, and smuggling activities. This market includes various technologies such as radar systems, satellite tracking, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and advanced analytics powered by AI to monitor, detect, and respond to illicit maritime activities. A substantial portion is dedicated to combating illegal drug trafficking due to the rising use of maritime routes for drug smuggling.

The European Union and European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA), along with other bodies like FRONTEX, are heavily investing in surveillance and security technologies, given that maritime drug smuggling remains a persistent challenge. For example, in 2021 alone, over 360 tons of cocaine were seized in Europe, much of it smuggled via maritime routes [10]. These activities drive demand for sophisticated surveillance tools specifically aimed at drug interdiction:

TAM, SAM and SOM for the customer group "Maritime Authorities" Use case scenario "preventing drug smuggling"	
Total Addressable Market (TAM): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> \$3.3 - 5 billion by 2028 worldwide \$2 - 3 billion by 2028 Europe 	<p>The broader maritime surveillance market is expected to reach \$33 billion by 2028, with a portion of that dedicated to drug trafficking prevention. A reasonable estimate is that 10-15% of the global maritime surveillance market is dedicated to drug smuggling prevention, which gives a TAM of \$3.3 billion to \$5 billion globally by 2028 [11].</p> <p>The TAM refers to all possible demand for solutions to prevent drug smuggling across European maritime borders.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maritime surveillance is critical for drug trafficking prevention, especially for key regions like the Mediterranean, North Sea, and the Atlantic coastlines.

TAM, SAM and SOM for the customer group "Maritime Authorities" Use case scenario "preventing drug smuggling"	
Total Addressable Market (continued):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Since drug trafficking is a significant portion of border enforcement, it is reasonable to estimate that 15-20% of the maritime surveillance market in Europe is dedicated to drug smuggling prevention [12]. This puts the TAM for drug smuggling prevention technologies at approximately \$2 to \$3 billion in Europe by 2028.
Serviceable Available Market (SAM): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> \$1 – 1.7 billion worldwide \$600 million to \$1,2 billion in Europe 	The SAM is the portion of the market that is relevant for the specific solutions being offered, focusing on where maritime surveillance technologies can be used for drug smuggling prevention. The European market is a significant region for maritime drug smuggling prevention, particularly in areas like the Mediterranean and the Atlantic where drugs often enter through Spain, Italy, and other coastal nations. Assuming Europe represents 30-35% of the global maritime surveillance market, the worldwide SAM for drug smuggling prevention in Europe could be valued at \$1 to \$1.7 billion by 2028. The European Union invests heavily in border and maritime security to curb drug smuggling. High-traffic regions, particularly southern European waters, require advanced technology for surveillance and interception. Given that a portion of the TAM will be for drug prevention surveillance technologies, SAM in Europe could realistically be 30-40% of the TAM, or roughly \$600 million to \$1.2 billion [11].
Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> \$100 million to \$340 million worldwide \$60 million to \$180 million in Europe 	The SOM estimates the portion of the SAM that could realistically be captured, considering competition, adoption barriers, and specific capabilities of companies offering maritime surveillance technologies. Market penetration for new entrants or niche technologies (like AI-powered systems, satellite monitoring, or unmanned surface and aerial vehicles) is likely to be 10-20% of the SAM in the near-to-midterm, depending on factors like regulatory approval, competition, and technology readiness. Thus, the SOM for exploiting maritime surveillance technologies for drug smuggling prevention in Europe could range between \$100 million to \$340 million by 2028 [11]. The SOM is the share of the SAM that can be captured by a company or organization within a specific timeframe, considering competition, market barriers, and scalability. The demand for new technologies such as AI-based surveillance, real-time data analytics, unmanned surface and aerial vehicles (USVs/UAVs), and interoperable multi-sensor systems is growing. If the company offering these technologies can achieve 10-15% market penetration within a few years, the SOM could be in the range of \$60 million to \$180 million in Europe.

TABLE 6: TAM, SAM, SOM FOR THE USE CASE SCENARIO "PREVENTING DRUG SMUGGLING"

These numbers reflect the growing demand for technologies in prevention of illegal immigration and drug trafficking across maritime borders, supported by governmental and law enforcement efforts to improve surveillance capabilities. For new entrants or emerging companies with innovative technologies, penetrating the maritime surveillance market can be challenging due to competition from existing suppliers, regulatory hurdles, and the slow adoption of new technologies in government-backed operations.

5.4 Market entry barriers

The description of the target markets also requires the analysis of market constraints and market entry challenges. When analysing market constraints and entry challenges for I-SEAMORE, especially in sensitive applications like preventing irregular migration and drug smuggling in Europe, several technical, regulatory, and ethical barriers emerge. These are summarised below. Understanding them is crucial as they can significantly influence adoption, scaling, and acceptance of I-SEAMORE solutions. By thoroughly addressing these challenges, I-SEAMORE aims to develop effective strategies for successful market adoption and sustained impact.

1. Ethical and Human Rights Considerations

Especially the use case “Preventing irregular migration” might be misunderstood or misused for monitoring asylum seekers and vulnerable populations, raising serious ethical red flags. The concerns are biased in AI-based identification or profiling, automated decision-making with life-altering implications, and potential for mission creep, i.e., using systems beyond originally intended scope. Therefore, I-SEAMORE’s architecture requires a clear governance structure for mission approval and review, including human oversight in AI outputs and transparent impact assessments. I-SEAMORE’s continuous SELP Landscape Assessment & Procedures Definition refers to these considerations and provides elements ensuring ethical readiness for the deployment of the project solutions. It showcases the practical implementation of ethical guidelines within the project, and it presents the activities performed by the main project bodies taking care of ethics and data governance. I-SEAMORE addresses aspects such as data privacy, AI explainability and fairness, consent and use limitation, accountability, and oversight as well as stakeholder engagement. The project ethical framework has foreseen assessments as a proactive approach towards the identification and management of ethical and, moreover, also of societal, legal, and privacy concerns.

2. Data Privacy and regulatory compliance

Surveillance operations in the maritime domain frequently involve the processing of sensitive personal data such as biometrics, vessel movements, and communications. Under the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), such processing requires a lawful basis, must be minimized, anonymized or pseudonymized, and carried out with transparency and accountability. For I-SEAMORE, this means all onboard and cloud-based systems must comply with data protection principles, particularly when integrating AI analytics and enabling cross-border data sharing. To this end, the consortium has prepared a Data Management Plan that sets procedures for collecting, storing, sharing, and preserving project data. Maritime surveillance faces additional complexity because it spans multiple legal frameworks worldwide, including uncertainties around AI and unmanned vehicle (UxV) regulations, which vary by country and may limit deployment. Political commitment is also essential, as some nations may be reluctant to invest in such systems without strong government mandates. Given I-SEAMORE’s positioning at the EU’s external borders and its international applicability, the system must comply with multiple overlapping jurisdictions. Legal issues extend to EU treaties such as Article 45 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU, which guarantees the free movement of persons.

At sea, maritime law is primarily based on international treaties. The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) establishes territorial waters up to 12 nautical miles, within which states exercise jurisdiction, subject to specific exceptions (e.g., criminal activity or illicit trafficking). Beyond this, states may act in the contiguous zone (up to 24 nautical miles) under certain conditions. Additional frameworks include the Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) Convention and the International Convention on Search and Rescue (SAR Convention), which mandates cooperation among neighbouring states in rescuing people in distress, even allowing entry into another state’s territorial waters for SAR purposes.

The European context is provided by Regulation 656/2014, which defines rules for detection, interception, and SAR activities in EU maritime border surveillance operations. Beyond maritime law, aviation law also applies to I-SEAMORE, as the system uses unmanned vehicles. In Europe, the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) regulates UAVs, including drone weight, altitude limits, and permitted flight zones.

Consequently, I-SEAMORE must operate within a highly complex legal landscape: ensuring GDPR compliance, navigating fragmented national and international maritime, aviation, and border security

laws, and aligning with EU treaties and international conventions. This requires strict data management procedures, ongoing regulatory monitoring, and strong governmental and cross-border cooperation to ensure lawful deployment and effective operation.

3. Comprehensibility and Reliability of Information

I-SEAMORE's complex AI data management and processing systems must present actionable insights to users with diverse backgrounds. This implies risk factor, i.e., AI-generated insights may be misinterpreted due to lack of context or explainability. An overreliance on systems can lead to false positives/negatives with operational or diplomatic consequences. Consequently, user interfaces must be intuitive, and AI outputs must be auditable, explainable, and embedded in standard operational procedures (SOPs).

These challenges include factors like comprehensibility and reliability of information. For exactly this reason also the high degree of data security is of utmost significance. Initiatives like the European Union maritime security regulations set the stage for I-SEAMORE's development within a strong governance framework.

Compliance with European data sovereignty and ethical principles ensures that the platform aligns with regulatory requirements, which is crucial for market adoption, particularly by government bodies concerned with data security. The following image provides an overview on regulations to be considered when taking the I-SEAMORE results to the market:

FIGURE 5: EXAMPLES OF REGULATORY REQUIREMENTS [13]

Apart from these mentioned challenges, further barriers for moving from pre-operational to full adaptation include solution maturity, applicability to different specific scenarios, and market acceptance. Factors such as development stage of product/system components, the technical complexities of ensuring earth observation (EO) data interoperability through a CISE-compliant adaptor, or diverse ways how the governments of European countries deal with immigration, count into it.

Beyond technical interfaces, there has to be a communication and dissemination strategy actively working to demystify complex technical solutions and AI applications for target stakeholders. Through accessible content formats, including webinars and other public engagement initiatives, awareness and understanding of the innovation applied in the use cases get ensured.

4. Technical and Operational Barriers

Maritime surveillance environments involve legacy systems, especially within governmental and inter-agency operations. The technical and operational barriers deal mainly with issues of interoperability and system integration. Bringing together multiple sensors, systems, and data sources from different providers

can be technically challenging. Also, the reliance on digital systems raises the risk of cyber threats, which may deter adoption if security is not robust. This obstacle may even be leveraged by the fact that the effectiveness of I-SEAMORE depends on real-time, high-quality data, while data-sharing restrictions or privacy concerns could limit its functionality. I-SEAMORE must integrate smoothly with existing command & control systems, and databases, and align with standards such as NATO STANAGs or EU CISE.

5. Market Adoption and Competition

There is an urgent need for demonstrable outcomes and solution maturity: profitability from stakeholders' point of view depends on clear benefits, such as improved border security and detection. And those benefits should be at a reasonable cost. High licensing and installation fees before proving full functionality, adaptability and effectiveness may deter early adopters.

In addition, there is competition from major defence contractors: companies like Thales (CoastShield) and Leonardo already have well-established maritime surveillance solutions (compare next chapter 6. Competition). Therefore, the customer values as well as the technical and business-related USPs must be clearly communicated. A thorough understanding is needed to identify segments where competitors are absent or unsuited. This is especially valid in the maritime industry, where traditional practices, high upfront costs, and unfamiliarity with advanced digital solutions could slow down adoption.

6. Geopolitical and Legal Constraints

Maritime domain awareness in Europe often requires cross-border coordination, subject to sovereignty concerns and fragmented jurisdictions (e.g., national navies, Frontex, EMSA). Even if I-SEAMORE has technical superiority, deployment may be blocked by political sensitivity or inter-agency friction.

7. Risk of Militarization Perception

Marketing I-SEAMORE to private contractors or using it for border surveillance may face backlash over the "militarization of migration control", especially in public opinion, NGOs and watchdog organizations and ethical investment filters. This could limit market growth or cause reputational damage unless proactively mitigated with responsible AI communication and ethical frameworks.

To this end, I-SEAMORE has established an engagement framework to ensure continuous interaction with relevant stakeholders across Europe, to explore emerging challenges, and identify practical solutions that align border management technologies with societal values and ethical standards.

8. Financial and Investment Barriers

I-SEAMORE customers need to secure investment for system integration and adaptation. This is a serious market entry barrier, especially in the light of budget limitations of public authorities: I-SEAMORE primarily targets government and state organizations, which may have constrained budgets and complex procurement processes. Consequently, governmental agencies and companies may struggle with the initial financial burden as well as with a long ROI Period: it may take considerable time before the system generates financial returns.

9. Organizational and Stakeholder Challenges

Customer Trust in an innovative technology: large contracts may require guarantees, and customers may hesitate to adopt solutions, which is newly deployed in the market. This is especially true, if more than one organisation offers the solution. Past experiences show that aligning multiple companies to offer a common product and service can be challenging due to differing interests and policies. Also, failure to continuously upgrade and expand I-SEAMORE's capabilities after the end of the project duration could lead to stagnation and reduced market relevance. Consequently, the development of profitable I-SEAMORE services faces market, financial, regulatory, technical, and organizational challenges. However, these barriers can be mitigated through:

- Strategic pricing models (e.g., loss-leading initial fees);
- A strong regulatory compliance framework;
- Effective market positioning and differentiation from competitors;
- Long-term funding strategies and government partnerships; and
- Robust cybersecurity and interoperability solutions.

We strongly believe that matching technological advancements with strong ethical standards, I-SEAMORE strives to become a model for responsible innovation deployment in critical infrastructure and security.

6 COMPETITION

The maritime surveillance market is highly competitive, with several major players offering solutions that focus on real-time monitoring, vessel tracking, and situational awareness. Companies such as Airbus, SAAB, Lockheed Martin, Boeing, IBM and Thales provide integrated maritime surveillance systems. I-SEAMORE will also face competition from companies involved in maritime security (MAST, Neptun Maritime Security, ESPADA, SPS Maritime Security, ThayerMahan, MUSC, Hudson Analytics, Solace Global). Furthermore, there are companies providing satellite imaging or other satellite-based services, while projects like Copernicus offer open-source data for monitoring. I-SEAMORE's differentiation lies in its integration of AI and data-fusion tools for interoperability and enhanced operational support, which could provide a competitive edge in more sophisticated and coordinated surveillance. For taking a more structured view on the competition and I-SEAMORE's competitive advantages, we will follow hereinafter our customer segmentation approach, looking at the identified key customer segments:

6.1 Competition for the use case scenario preventing illegal immigration

When narrowing the competitive landscape to maritime surveillance solutions addressing illegal immigration for maritime authorities, I-SEAMORE faces competition from both major defence contractors and specialized surveillance platforms. Below is a tailored breakdown of key competitors, their positioning, and how I-SEAMORE compares:

Company / Project	Solution	Differentiation	Comparison to I-SEAMORE
Airbus Defence and Space	STYRIS Maritime Surveillance System	Integrated coastal surveillance, vessel tracking, radar + AIS fusion	Mature system with broad deployment; lacks native AI-driven mission support interoperability
Leonardo	ATHENA-C2, Seon, and SAGE integrated surveillance solutions	Multi-domain C2 systems, including for migration control missions	Strong in ISR; I-SEAMORE may be more agile and adaptable to multi-authority collaboration
Elbit Systems	Seagull, Hermes UAVs, maritime C4ISR	Heavy focus on unmanned assets and naval ISR	I-SEAMORE benefits from greater platform interoperability across authorities and EU systems
Indra Sistemas	SIVE (Sistema Integrado de Vigilancia Exterior) for Spain's Guardia Civil	Border surveillance system combining radar, EO/IR, and maritime intelligence	I-SEAMORE is more flexible and scalable beyond national deployments
Thales	Coast Watcher 100 / Maritime Surveillance Solutions	Combines radars, C2 centres, UAVs, and ISR tools	Similar scale, but typically tailored for state military; less modular than I-SEAMORE
HENSOLDT	XPACT Radar, ARGOSIA naval ISR systems	High-performance radars, modular naval C2 systems	More hardware-centric; I-SEAMORE integrates these with enhanced mission orchestration tools

Company / Project	Solution	Differentiation	Comparison to I-SEAMORE
SAAB AB	Coastal Surveillance System (CSS)	Radar, EO/IR sensors, and vessel tracking integrated into national surveillance networks	Proven reliability, but less emphasis on AI/Big Data decision support
Frontex + Eurosur Fusion Services	EU border control agency tools, data fusion through Copernicus and national authorities	Shared situational awareness across EU borders	I-SEAMORE can interoperate with Eurosur, but also expands use cases with UxV and AI synergy
UnseenLabs / Spire / Kleos Space	Commercial RF and AIS satellite data providers for dark ship tracking	Specialize in identifying non-cooperative vessels (e.g. migrants or smugglers)	Complementary to I-SEAMORE's data fusion layer; potential partners, not direct competitors

TABLE 7: KEY COMPETITORS FOR I-SEAMORE IN THE USE CASE "PREVENTING ILLEGAL IMMIGRATION"

6.2 Competition for the use case scenario preventing drug smuggling

For the specific use case of "preventing illegal drug smuggling", the competitive landscape shifts slightly compared to illegal immigration, as the emphasis moves more toward interdiction support, cargo anomaly detection, pattern analysis, and real-time interdiction coordination—often involving defence contractors, coast guards, and border protection systems with stronger SIGINT, long-range radar, and AI-enabled predictive analytics. Here is a breakdown of specific competitors relevant to maritime authorities in this use case:

Company / Project	Solution	Differentiation	Comparison to I-SEAMORE
Elbit Systems – Seagull / Hermes 900 Maritime Patrol	Advanced UAV/USV systems, maritime patrol drones with SIGINT and COMINT payloads	Strong match: capable of tracking and intercepting suspicious vessels using UAVs.	Competes on UxV deployment, but weaker AI/data fusion
Thales – Maritime Mission Systems (MMS)	Combines radar, sonar, AIS analysis, and electronic surveillance	Good fit: designed for detecting low-profile or dark vessels often used in smuggling.	Direct competitor on interoperability and command systems
Indra – SIVE	Border surveillance system used by Spanish Guardia Civil; integrates radar, IR, AIS, and cameras	Proven in anti-smuggling operations around the Strait of Gibraltar.	Less advanced on big data or UxV deployment flexibility
SAAB – Giraffe AMB / Sea Giraffe / CoastWatch	Surface and air surveillance radar, multi-domain C2 systems	Moderate fit; strong integration with navies.	Lacks deep AI/data fusion compared to I-SEAMORE

Company / Project	Solution	Differentiation	Comparison to I-SEAMORE
Leonardo – ATHENA-C2 + Falco UAV	Real-time decision support, EO/IR payloads, automated target detection	Strong for operational planning and tactical interdiction missions	Less focused on open-source data or UxV orchestration
HENSOLDT – Xpeller and Radar Systems	Counter-UxV systems and sea surveillance radars	Limited fit: more focused on port/area defence than long-range smuggling detection.	More hardware-centric; I-SEAMORE integrates these with enhanced mission orchestration tools
Copernicus EMS (with FRONTEX)	Open-source EO data and ship detection via satellites (Sentinel series)	Supportive role: used for wide-area monitoring but lacks real-time interdiction capability.	Complementary—not a direct competitor
Spire / Kleos / UnseenLabs (RF/EO Analytics from Space)	RF geolocation, dark vessel detection, pattern-of-life analysis	Very good at detecting vessels operating without AIS – a smuggling hallmark.	Limited end-to-end mission integration or UxV control

TABLE 8: KEY COMPETITORS FOR I-SEAMORE IN THE "PREVENTING DRUG SMUGGLING" USE CASE

6.3 Competitive advantages and unique selling propositions

In many industries, digitalization impacts and changes the traditional business models of companies sometimes seriously. Digitalisation and the associated ICT solutions bring numerous advantages and opportunities. The basis here is the usability of data. By analysing the data relevant to the academia, business, or industry, to private or public entities, internal processes can be made significantly more efficient. This primarily affects the efficiency and effectiveness of value creation also in the I-SEAMORE business creation.

As shown in the previous sub-chapters, on the market side, a great diversity in customer preferences (both across and within countries), factor prices depending on resilience of international value chains, as well as heightened regulation (notably on data security, data governance, ethics, etc.) further increase the challenges for players looking to gain market share in the maritime surveillance and in related sectors. Consequently, the I-SEAMORE commercial deployment also implies several risks:

- Procurement in the governmental sector depends on budgets available at national or regional level; therefore, it risks being financially less affordable than systems with less integrated features, functions and less impacted values;
- There are also technological risks: high maintenance, technical updates, technology advancements, hardware updates, ensuring compatibility, ensuring adequate sensor accuracy, etc.;
- And trust risks also exist: can the system be seen as reliable enough that it can be used as the only solution?
- With larger scale adoption, educating the users adequately is also a risk factor.

The situational awareness technologies of I-SEAMORE add not only the described technical and business values to customers' supply chains and value delivery services. Moreover, they reduce the risk of undetected threats or incidents for the target customer groups. Also taking those circumstances into consideration, the competitive advantages of I-SEAMORE's future products and services can be summarised as follows:

- **Aligning Features with Needs:** Ensures that the architecture system's features (e.g., surveillance technology, data analytics, communication tools) directly address the specific jobs, pains, and gains of target customers.
- **Trusted Information for Decision Support:** Provide the means (=platform) to link currently isolated data and disparate applications, between hardware providers, software providers, service providers and data providers, within countries and across borders, in an efficient manner, adhering to international regulations and interoperability standards. Enable the storage and access of maritime surveillance information in trusted and collaborative infrastructures, with elasticity to scale and with a proper legal basis (consent, anonymization, etc.).
- **AI-enhanced operational intelligence:** Unlike many legacy or hardware-centric systems, I-SEAMORE's native use of AI for threat detection, anomaly analysis, and multi-source data fusion gives it a functional edge in identifying illegal operation patterns, including dark vessels.
- **Interoperability and multi-dimensional:** To enable components of the system to function individually and to interact with each other as well as with other data systems: I-SEAMORE allows integration of Copernicus, AIS, EO, RF, and UAV data—enabling a broader and more agile approach.
- **Adaptability:** The platform adapts to the evolving needs of the various stakeholders across different requirement levels, allowing seamless integration with heterogeneous systems (civilian and defence).
- **Scalability:** I-SEAMORE allows integration of further modules thanks to a modular architecture based on standards that allows future vertical⁷ and horizontal⁸ scalability, i.e., agile support for joint civilian–military use cases.
- **Multi-vendor:** Designed with Maritime Operation Centres (MOCs) and joint authority missions in mind, I-SEAMORE natively supports (in addition to its modular interoperability) multi-country, multi-agency collaboration – a feature most defence-contractor systems do not prioritize. The platform allows monitoring several different parameters thus overcoming potential issues of vendor-login. The system, which has been engineered to be intrinsically brand neutral, allows access to data collected by different sources/devices, thus providing an integrated view for decision support on maritime surveillance.
- Enabling **Cooperative Business Models:** Implement clear governance for the use of data/information on individual, regional, national, and European level all along value chains in many verticals for research, for commercial and for governmental use by respecting the legal requirements (GDPR, EU Data Governance Act et al.).
- **Ethical and Co-Creation-Driven Design:** Whereas many systems are focused on technical capability, I-SEAMORE actively promotes co-creation, user-centric validation, and ethical compliance, increasingly demanded in EU border operations.
- **Ensuring Border Protection, Border Security and Sovereignty:** Provide decision support services as a framework to implement the European Border protection and border security at scale, in a compliant, secure, and trustable manner.
- **Demonstrating Impact:** The system enhances border control effectiveness, improves efficiency, and contributes to national security.

Europe's digital transformation is changing the way customers access maritime surveillance and decision support systems, products, and services. Although this sector has experienced a degree of change in recent years, the constant preparation of technology-driven applications is something new. I-SEAMORE is a highly innovative concept, and its commercial exploitation shall be multidimensional ensuring maximum awareness towards its target stakeholders. In summary, the scenarios in the tested use cases illustrate that the following elements can be considered as I-SEAMORE's USPs:

⁷ other application areas in other market segments

⁸ other use cases and applications possible in maritime border protection

Unique Selling Proposition	Why it matters
Automation and speed of detection	Disruptive technologies are being integrated into one system that can even be further developed to suggest decisions and to initiate follow-up actions on detected circumstances
Comprehensive situational awareness and decision support	Tools that support mission planning, threat detection, and operational response and enormous volume of data to be managed for decision support
Interoperability	System's ability to integrate with legacy systems, NATO protocols, and multi-agency tools, enabling integration with customs, drug enforcement databases (e.g., INTERPOL, EUROPOL), or coast guard systems
Integration of multiple assets and multi-domain integration	Illegal operations often use multiple fast boats or transshipment tactics. The Ability to deploy, manage, and coordinate aerial/surface unmanned assets gives I-SEAMORE an edge
Real-time mission support through real-time high-resolution data accessibility	Since interdiction is time-sensitive – decision loops must be extremely short.
AI-driven data fusion from multiple sources	Use of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data for real-time insight generation allows advanced anomaly detection & threat analysis
Market Reach	Usage of Earth Observation, RF/AIS, SAR, and satellite imagery in surveillance; compliance with industry standards; end-user driven; and geographic and customer diversity

TABLE 9: I-SEAMORE'S USPS AND WHY THEY MATTER

These USPs reflect many main capabilities of the I-SEAMORE system, which is more than the ability to respond to existing customer challenges and to adapt quickly to varying requirements. The use of cutting-edge technologies and alignment with EU policy frameworks strengthens its competitive standing in the evolving landscape of maritime security solutions.

7 MARKETING, SALES AND DISTRIBUTION

The goal of I-SEAMORE's exploitation is to bring the innovative system or its elements to the market. Within this document, we illustrated that I-SEAMORE will allow new business models across the value chain from data gathering (data collection), via data fusion services, data analytics, data visualisation, data communication, to services and supply for data-driven decision support. As a result, direct end customers, system integrators, resellers as well as innovative service providers will receive direct and indirect support to find their place within the maritime surveillance activities and system and the related value chains.

Consequently, I-SEAMORE will enable effective business models that may impose novel solutions in the target markets, I-SEAMORE has the potential to reduce cost (e.g., in the case of avoided helicopter operations), to increase the range of services that can be provided, to improve service and information quality and to allow for more efficient information analytics as well as for service and information provision. For every individual role, it is crucial to understand the value creation and value capturing by individual participants, and the overall value created. This overall value created is a governed secure data and information exchange for an improved surveillance of the maritime environment. In order to make business models sustainable principles such as "sharing" and "smart services" should be considered: "Sharing" in the value chain means to involve all stakeholders who are connected to each other [14]. These identified

stakeholders perform interactions and services, and, if those are well combined, added value can be created. To meet the constantly increasing needs and expectations of customers, the principle of “Smart Service” should be regarded as a solution. These are often more complex bunch of services that contribute to improved support for its users. On a platform like I-SEAMORE there is the option that other value adding partners can be included. The more service you could offer to your customers, the more value can be generated [15]. Interactions within partnerships are described as value propositions in the referring chapter above.

Maritime Authorities as target users and customers considered within this document, define the initial target segment for I-SEAMORE, meaning the typical initial customers of the products and services. Those very same end users will most probably change over time their needs according to changing challenges. For this reason, it is possible to introduce later additional upgrades or further development of the system. The services include all special activities associated with the purchase of the systems, such as installation (compensated by one-time installation fees), maintenance (compensated by quarterly, or annual recurring fees), software-as-a-service or data-as-a-service, and training-on-the-system.

The assumption that products cannot develop their value until they are used (“value-in-use”), i.e., through the service itself, could be seen as evidence that there is no clear distinction between product and service. Therefore, one-time purchasing costs for the data gathering systems may also be computed into monthly, quarterly, or annual fees to simplify customers’ tendering and procuring processes.

7.1 Distribution and sales strategy

Based on the detailed technical and operational capabilities of the I-SEAMORE ecosystem and to harvest from its market potential, an effective distribution and sales strategy should reflect the system's complexity, regulatory context, and public sector focus. Below is a comprehensive strategy structured around key pillars.

Given I-SEAMORE's alignment with Maritime Operation Centres (MOCs) and public authorities across the EU, the core distribution model should be Direct-to-Government (D2G). It should rely on direct contracts with national authorities (e.g., Coast Guards, Ministries of Defence, Border and Customs Agencies). Furthermore, framework agreements with the European Commission (e.g., DG MARE, EMSA, Frontex) and regional agencies would support this strategy. It is also suggested to position the I-SEAMORE system or its core elements on public procurement platforms such as TED (Tenders Electronic Daily) and the EU Defence Fund (EDF) project pipelines.

To achieve this, a reference architecture pack should be developed to meet public procurement requirements. It should be complemented by secure certifications related to cybersecurity, ethics, data governance, and interoperability (CISE-compliance). Since the IP used in the I-SEAMORE system has different IP owners, an Exploitation Agreement template has been developed during the project, which is available to all I-SEAMORE partners. Any kind of this so-called “bundle deployment” may be accompanied by long-term service-level agreements (SLAs) into the core offering.

Relevant **Go-to-Market channels** could be pilot programs and reference sites, EU funding mechanisms, or public-private innovation platforms:

- **Pilot Programs & Reference Sites** could leverage early-stage deployments at select MOCs as lighthouse projects or could be achieved by offering joint trials with Frontex, EMSA or regional sea-border authorities.
- **EU Funding Mechanisms** can be used to embed I-SEAMORE in consortia applying for Horizon Europe, CEF, EIT, or EDIDP/EDF calls. Co-funding could also be available through Interreg or Blue Economy initiatives for multi-country operations.

- Through **Public-Private Innovation Platforms**, I-SEAMORE could engage i.e. in Digital Ocean Twin, Blue Data Spaces, Gaia-X Data Spaces, and CISE Working Groups to advocate for standardization and promote the platform's interoperability strength.

Another applicable distribution and sales model can be implemented through **strategic partnerships**. The following table suggests partner types to collaborate with for scaling the adoption of I-SEAMORE or its components across Europe and beyond. Especially, collaborations with companies involved in defence and intelligence operations can open new revenue streams and increase market penetration:

Partner type	Examples	Role in distribution
System Integrators	GMV, Leonardo, Atos, Thales	Embed I-SEAMORE into wider command and control (C2) suites
National Defence Contractors	Kongsberg, Saab, Elbit Systems	Localize and certify for national infrastructure
Satellite & EO Providers	CLS, Spire, Planet, EUSPA actors	Co-develop data service bundles
Port Security Vendors	Hensoldt, Pole Star, SRT Marine	Embed in port and logistics surveillance chains

TABLE 10: EXAMPLES FOR STRATEGIC PARTNERSHIPS FOR I-SEAMORE DISTRIBUTION

Initiatives like Gaia-X and European Union ethics, data, and maritime security regulations set the stage for I-SEAMORE's development within a strong governance framework. Compliance with European data sovereignty principles ensures that the platform aligns with regulatory requirements, which is crucial for market adoption, particularly by government bodies concerned with data security.

Consequently, the sales strategy should be enabled by focussing on the target customer segments and the segment-oriented value propositions. For MOCs the emphasis should be put on system orchestration, threat detection, and mission support. For ministries/other governmental agencies interoperability, EU and ethical compliance, and cost-effectiveness should be highlighted, whilst for private contractors (security/shipping specific service modules (e.g., AI-based threat prediction, AIS fusion, etc.) under licensing or SaaS models may be offered. This segment-specific sales strategy would then allow a range of pricing models:

- Core licensing for the orchestration platform;
- Tiered modules for unmanned asset management, data gathering, analytics, visualisation or data fusion;
- Annual maintenance and updates package (with cyber patching and AI model tuning); and eventually accompanied by
- Optional Managed Service offerings (cloud-hosted or hybrid edge-cloud).

This sales strategy may be accompanied by scaling initiatives, e.g., the white-labelling for defence OEMs, enabling OEM partners to incorporate the I-SEAMORE core under their branding in joint tenders.

In addition, post-deployment training and certification can support sales and scaling by offerings certified training courses for MOC staff and UxV operators.

The following table provides a summary overview on potential distribution channels and its individual distribution objectives:

Strategy Pillar	Objective
Direct D2G Sales	Build trust with national authorities and secure contracts
Strategic Partnerships	Integrate into existing surveillance ecosystems
EU-Level Programs	Fund deployments and validate cross-border use cases
Modular Licensing	Adapt to diverse user profiles (authorities, ports, etc.)
Lighthouse Projects	Demonstrate value with real-world operational impact

TABLE 11: EXAMPLES FOR I-SEAMORE DISTRIBUTION CHANNELS

7.2 Communication and PR strategy

For a highly technical and mission-critical system like I-SEAMORE, a tailored communication and PR strategy must reflect the platform’s dual role: supporting public good (security, border protection, environmental monitoring) and showcasing European technological sovereignty. For these purposes, we identified the following goals and objectives for the promotional and PR activities:

- To position I-SEAMORE as a flagship EU maritime innovation project by emphasizing its role in supporting European digital autonomy, maritime resilience, and cross-border cooperation.
- To encourage engagement from tech providers, research institutions, and private operators by prioritising a better dialogue between the public and private sector; including the academic environment (research centres and universities), the local community, NGOs, institutions (public and private), and stronger public-private partnerships;
- To co-ordinate activities of all stakeholders with a diverse set of communications methods (public relations, bulletins, newsletter, website, etc.);
- To build trust with institutional and public stakeholders to make sure that transparency and credibility are key for adoption by government and defence sectors;
- To collaborate with governmental agencies and all national public structures and authorities to achieve maximum exposure for collaborating organizations and other stakeholders. This can be accomplished by showcasing results and real-world impact, by communicating operational success stories, field deployment updates, and user testimonials.

It is also suggested to facilitate collaboration among different groups of stakeholders to enhance uptake of I-SEAMORE results and integration of different and diverse end-user knowledge as well as to prepare scientific articles and conference presentations. By implementing the illustrated communication and PR strategy across the diverse ecosystem of stakeholders, the following core messaging themes could be addressed:

- **“EU-made technology for European maritime safety”** – emphasis on sovereignty and regional trust.
- **“Situational awareness without compromise”** – highlight technical advantage.
- **“From seabed to sky – connected, automated, and secure”** – captures system integration.
- **“Empowering operations, enhancing decisions”** – for operator-centric messaging.
- **“AI and unmanned systems working for public safety”** – simplified narrative for wider audiences.

When applying these different communication means, it is of utmost importance to target the very heterogeneous stakeholder and potential customer groups by segmenting the communication audience properly:

Audience	Core Messages
EU institutions (DG MARE, DG DEFIS, EMSA, Frontex, EDA)	Strategic enabler of border safety, innovation, and data-sharing.
National authorities / MOCs	Secure, scalable, interoperable platform tailored for European missions.
Industry partners (integrators, UxV manufacturers, ports)	Plug-and-play architecture; interoperability with their assets and systems.
Maritime tech ecosystem & researchers	Open, collaborative platform aligned with EU data and AI initiatives.
Public & media	Enhancing safety, sovereignty, and surveillance with ethical AI.

TABLE 12: AUDIENCE SEGMENTATION IN I-SEAMORE'S COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

8 CONCLUSIONS

Definitions of "business model" vary, but most people would agree that it describes how a company creates and captures value. Our business modelling approach exemplifies how to design collaborative models between stakeholders and an I-SEAMORE partner entity providing the I-SEAMORE system and related services. The features of the model define the customer value proposition, which then will lead to consider the exploitation mechanisms, indicating how a value delivery entity will organize itself and whom it will partner with to produce value, and specify how it will structure its supply chain.

The core of the I-SEAMORE 's multi-sided model is the value created by the interactions of multiple organizations, including hardware provider, provider of core services (data fusion, data integration, exchange etc.), data provider, provider of business applications, provider of compliance services, provider of enabling services, as well as data receivers and consumers of the mentioned services. Principles and rules need to be set according to the business-case pattern to help governing and coordinating the contributing organizations that will use the I-SEAMORE system to meet its objectives and progress through the different life-cycle stages. These rules and principles are set by the architecture framework, which has been developed.

The analysis and synthesis results show that several types of value-generation chains may be built for successful deployment of I-SEAMORE. However, these services and solutions could be beneficial for many different key target groups, e.g., government and border agencies, local authorities, civil protection agencies, etc., interested not necessarily on the entire system solution, but also in elements of the system architecture. In conclusions, the I-SEAMORE system can be exploited successfully if it creates value for the involved organizations that – the following the logic of multi-sided business models – use information and generate knowledge in data-driven applications. Within those settings the I-SEAMORE system – if operated as strong and collaborative platform – is enabled to unlock the potential for following benefits:

- **Multi-Sided Platform:** Platform business models revolve around creating an ecosystem that connects multiple groups or "sides." These sides can include producers, consumers, developers, partners, and more.
- **Two-Way Value Flow:** Unlike linear models, platforms facilitate interactions and value exchanges between multiple parties. Users on one side can interact with and create value for users on the other side.
- **Network Effects:** Platform models often leverage network effects, where the value of the platform increases as more participants join. This encourages growth and can create a self-reinforcing cycle.

- **Facilitator Role:** The entity orchestrating I-SEAMORE value delivery in the future will act as a facilitator that provides the infrastructure, tools, and rules for interactions to occur. It does not necessarily produce all the goods or services itself.
- **Diverse Revenue Streams:** Platform businesses can generate revenue from various sources, including transaction fees, subscriptions, advertising, data monetization, and more.
- **Scalability:** Platforms can scale more rapidly because the focus is on expanding the user base and enhancing interactions rather than linear production and distribution.

As a result, I-SEAMORE will create reusable and scalable value-added services. In this regard, I-SEAMORE will reflect the need of unification of many single technology solutions in the relevant sectors. The key to success will be ensuring that I-SEAMORE delivers clear, measurable benefits while navigating regulatory complexities and securing long-term stakeholder trust. Thus, the commercialisation success factors will be:

- **Embed Ethics & Privacy by Design** into all system layers and application (AI, UX, storage, consent).
- **Include human-in-the-loop validation** in all AI-influenced decisions.
- **Establish transparency mechanisms:** log usage, provide audits, and offer “explain AI decision” functions.
- **Pilot deployments with strong oversight** (e.g., EU-funded public-private partnerships with clear boundaries).
- **Engage with NGOs, legal experts, and public stakeholders** in all phases of development to build trust and reduce backlash.
- **Seamless interoperability and adherence to standards:** Emphasize and ensure I-SEAMORE's smooth integration with existing command & control systems, databases, and sensor networks. Strict alignment with international and European standards (e.g., CISE, NATO STANAGs) is paramount. This minimizes technical and operational barriers, reduces integration complexities for adopters, and builds confidence among public authorities who prioritize standardized solutions.
- **Clear Value Proposition & Competitive Differentiation:** Articulate I-SEAMORE's Unique Selling Propositions (USPs) clearly. This involves identifying specific market segments where I-SEAMORE offers unique advantages over established competitors (e.g., Thales, Leonardo), focusing on its strengths in AI, Big Data fusion, and heterogeneous asset integration for enhanced maritime and border surveillance.

The estimated time that it will take the joint exploitable result to reach the market will be long. It requires the development of go-to-market strategy, with segmentation and prioritization of target customers, with a pricing strategy, with a distribution strategy and with a communication strategy, including the creation of marketing materials. We believe in the future commercial success in I-SEAMORE key results, and we will contribute to combing all these different actions to lay the ground for sustainable future operations.

REFERENCES

- [1] FRONTEX: Risk Analysis for 2023/2024, Warsaw, 2023, ISBN 978-92-9467-894-2
- [2] <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1082077/deaths-of-migrants-in-the-mediterranean-sea/>, accessed on 29/08/2025
- [3] Council of Europe Work in the Field of Crime Problems, Council of Europe Publication, Strasbourg, 1998
- [4] FRONTEX: Risk Analysis for 2023/2024, Warsaw, 2023, ISBN 978-92-9467-894-2
- [5] <https://iseamore-project.eu/public-deliverable/>; lastly accessed on 29/08/2025
- [6] <https://www.b2binternational.com/research/methods/faq/what-is-the-value-proposition-canvas/>; lastly accessed on 29/08/2025
- [7] Technavio. (2024). Maritime security market: Global industry analysis and forecast (2024–2028); retrieved from <https://www.technavio.com/report/maritime-security-market-industry-analysis>; lastly accessed on 29/08/2025
- [8] Grand View Research. (2025). Europe maritime surveillance market outlook: 2018–2030
- [9] Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y., Bernarda, G., Smith, A., & Papadakos, T. (2014). Value Proposition Design: How to Create Products and Services Customers Want. John Wiley & Sons
- [10] Independent. (2023). Record amounts of cocaine are being seized in Europe. The Independent.; retrieved from Independent.co.uk; lastly accessed on 01/09/2025
- [11] Business Research Company. (2024). Maritime surveillance market size, share & growth forecast (2024–2028); retrieved from Business Research Company insights
- [12] International Chamber of Shipping. (2023). Container Inspection Rates and Implications for Smuggling. Quoting Europol report
- [13] Otto, Boris; Seidelmann, Joachim; Schmelting, Jürgen; Sauer, Olaf (2023): Manufacturing-X Data Space Study. Architecture, basic services and organization, taking into account the specific features of the equipment industry. VDMA. Frankfurt a.M; retrieved from https://www.zvei.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Presse_und_Medien/Pressebereich/2023_059_Manufacturing_X/Manufacturing_X_Data_Space_Study_ZVEI-VDMA-Fraunhofer.pdf, lastly accessed on 15.08.2025
- [14] Prahalad, C. K., & Ramaswamy, V. (2004): The Future of Competition: Co-Creating Unique Value with Customers. Harvard Business School Press
- [15] Vargo, S. L., & Lusch, R. F. (2004): Evolving to a new dominant logic for marketing. Journal of Marketing, 68(1), 1–17; retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.68.1.1.24036>; lastly accessed on 28.08.25

LIST OF ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
App	Application
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CEC	Commission of the European Economic Communities
CISE	Common Information Sharing Environment
D2G	Direct -to-Government
DaaS	Data as as Service
EC	European Commission
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
e.g.	Example given
EMSA	Emergency Medical Services Alliance
EO	Earth Observation
Et al.	et alia (and others)
EU	European Union
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
GCS	Ground Control Station
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
HW	Hardware
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
i.e.	id est (that is)
IP	Intellectual Property
IT	Information Technology
MOC	Maritime Operations Centers
n/a	not applicable
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
R&D	Research and Development
RF	Radio Frequency
RTO	Research and Technology Organizations
S&R , SAR	Search and Rescue
SAM	Serviceable Available Market
SIGINT	Signals Intelligence
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SOLAS	International Convention for the Safety of Life at Sea
SOM	Serviceable Obtainable Market
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
STANAG	Standardization Agreement
SW	Software
TAM	Total Available Market
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TED	Tenders Electronic Daily
UAV	Unmanned Air Vehicle
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
USP	Unique Selling Proposition
USV	Unmanned Surface Vehicle
UxV	Unmanned Vehicle
WP	Work Package

LIST OF TABLES

<i>Table 1: Use case no 1: Preventing irregular migration.....</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>Table 2: Use case no 2: Preventing smuggling of drugs.....</i>	<i>11</i>
<i>Table 3: Overview on key customer values for Maritime Authorities.....</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>Table 4: Key customer values and referring exploitation models.....</i>	<i>17</i>
<i>Table 5: TAM, SAM, SOM for the use case scenario "Preventing illegal immigration".....</i>	<i>19</i>
<i>Table 6: TAM, SAM, SOM for the use case scenario "Preventing drug smuggling".....</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Table 7: Key competitors for I-SEAMORE in the use case "Preventing illegal immigration".....</i>	<i>25</i>
<i>Table 8: Key competitors for I-SEAMORE in the "Preventing drug smuggling" use case.....</i>	<i>26</i>
<i>Table 9: I-SEAMORE's USPs and why they matter.....</i>	<i>28</i>
<i>Table 10: Examples for strategic partnerships for I-SEAMORE distribution.....</i>	<i>30</i>
<i>Table 11: Examples for I-SEAMORE distribution channels.....</i>	<i>31</i>
<i>Table 12: Audience segmentation in I-SEAMORE's communication strategy.....</i>	<i>32</i>

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1: Key stakeholders in the value-generation chain in the surveillance market.....</i>	<i>6</i>
<i>Figure 2: Architecture of the I-SEAMORE ecosystem.....</i>	<i>8</i>
<i>Figure 3: Number of recorded deaths of migrants in the Mediterranean Sea 2014 to 2024.....</i>	<i>9</i>
<i>Figure 4: Possible I-Seamore use cases.....</i>	<i>12</i>
<i>Figure 5: Examples of regulatory requirements.....</i>	<i>22</i>